

Acceptance of Injectable Contraception at Tertiary Care Hospital**Nalini I. Anand¹, Mona Gandhi², Trupti Nayak², Darshita Parmar³**¹Professor and Head, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Shri M.P. Shah Government Medical College, Jamnagar²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Shri M.P. Shah Government Medical College, Jamnagar³2nd Year Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Shri M.P. Shah Government Medical College, Jamnagar

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Abstract:

Introduction: India's rapid population growth has posed significant challenges, with family planning being essential to improving maternal and child health. Despite efforts since the launch of the Family Planning Programme in 1952, a large unmet need for contraception persists, particularly for spacing methods. Injectable contraceptives like DMPA, introduced in 2015, offer a long-acting, reversible option. However, acceptance is influenced by factors such as socioeconomic status, education, and cultural beliefs, highlighting the need for increased awareness and counseling to promote their use.

Materials and Methods: This prospective cohort study included 175 reproductive-age women attending a tertiary care hospital between January and December 2023. Participants, including postpartum women, were carefully selected, excluding those with permanent contraception or chronic health conditions. DMPA (150 mg) was administered intramuscularly every three months. Counseling on side effects, follow-up schedules, and compliance was provided. Data were analyzed using SPSS, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$, to assess demographic trends, acceptance, and outcomes related to DMPA use.

Results: In our study, the majority of participants (45.2%) were aged 21-25 years, with urban residents comprising 62.8% of the sample. Most women (70%) had some level of education, and 60% were from nuclear families. In terms of parity, 49.3% had two children, and 72% had two or more children, indicating completed family size. Regarding side effects, irregular bleeding was the most common (60%), followed by weight gain (17.7%), while 8% of participants reported no issues with DMPA use. The primary reason for acceptance was the convenience of not requiring daily administration (49.7%), and 28% appreciated its compatibility with breastfeeding. However, discontinuation after the first injection was high (54.8%), with side effects (40%) and loss to follow-up (18.3%) being the main reasons for attrition. Mood changes were the least reported reason for discontinuation (1.7%), and discontinuation decreased steadily with subsequent doses.

Conclusion: DMPA is an effective and convenient contraceptive option, particularly appreciated for its ease of use and compatibility with breastfeeding. However, side effects and follow-up challenges highlight the need for enhanced counseling and support to improve long-term adherence and reduce discontinuation rates.

Keywords: Injectable contraception, DMPA, Family planning, Contraceptive adherence.

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Introduction

India's population explosion has posed significant challenges since its independence. Family planning plays a crucial role in addressing this issue by promoting the health of individuals and the community. [1] However, acceptance of contraception is influenced by several factors, including socioeconomic status, education, cultural beliefs, and family dynamics. [2] Despite the availability of various contraceptive methods, many women in India do not use any form of contraception, contributing to a high number of unintended pregnancies and maternal risks. [3]

India was the first country to launch a Family Planning Programme in 1952, focusing initially on population control. [4] Over time, the program evolved to prioritize maternal and child health, promoting safe birth spacing and reducing unsafe pregnancies. With the high maternal morbidity linked to the lack of contraception, the usage of family planning methods can prevent over 30% of maternal deaths. [5] Yet, a significant unmet need for contraception persists, particularly in spacing methods like condoms, IUDs, and oral pills. [6]

Injectable contraceptives, such as DMPA (Depot Medroxyprogesterone Acetate), were introduced

into India's National Family Planning Programme in 2015 to address the gap in contraception options. [7] Administered every three months as an intramuscular injection, DMPA, also known as the Antara Injection, offers a reversible, long-acting alternative to oral contraceptives and IUDs. [8] The addition of injectable contraception enhances the range of family planning choices, aligning with national goals to reduce unmet contraceptive needs and improve maternal health outcomes.

Materials and Methods

This prospective cohort study was conducted to evaluate the acceptance of injectable contraception among women attending the outpatient department at a tertiary care hospital. The study included 175 non-pregnant women of reproductive age, ranging from January 2023 to December 2023. Participants were carefully selected to include women who had one or more children, including those in the postpartum period. The focus was to assess acceptance and use of injectable contraceptives among women who had the potential need for family planning and birth spacing. Personal demographic details such as name, age, address, occupation, and other relevant information were collected during the initial patient interviews.

Women meeting specific exclusion criteria were not included in the study. These criteria included those with permanent contraception methods like tubal ligation, women with undiagnosed uterine bleeding, and those diagnosed with chronic medical conditions, such as hypertension, vascular diseases, diabetes, breast cancer, liver disease, or rheumatic heart disease (RHD). This selection ensured that the study group consisted of healthy reproductive-age women without any conditions that could contraindicate the use of injectable contraception.

The injectable contraceptive used in this study was Depot Medroxyprogesterone Acetate (DMPA) 150 mg, administered as an intramuscular injection every three months. This contraceptive method, also known as the Antara Injection, is a long-

acting, reversible contraceptive. Patients were counseled regarding the dosing schedule, the importance of regular follow-up, and potential side effects associated with the use of DMPA. Proper education about compliance and timely administration was provided to enhance acceptance and adherence.

Throughout the study period, participants were monitored for any complications or side effects related to the use of injectable contraception. Common side effects of DMPA, such as irregular bleeding, weight gain, and mood changes, were addressed with conservative management strategies. Patients who experienced any adverse effects were treated accordingly and followed up to ensure resolution of symptoms.

The data collected from the study participants, including demographic profiles, compliance with contraceptive schedules, and outcomes in terms of contraception success or complications, were analyzed to assess the level of acceptance and satisfaction with DMPA. This information will help inform future contraceptive programs and strategies aimed at improving family planning services in tertiary care settings.

Data from 175 participants were analyzed using SPSS version 21.1. Descriptive statistics like mean, standard deviation, and percentages summarized demographic data. Categorical variables were analyzed using Chi-square or Fisher's exact tests, while continuous variables were assessed with independent t-tests or ANOVA. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

In our study, the majority of participants were aged between 21-25 years (45.2%), followed by 26-30 years (25.2%). Most women (62.8%) resided in urban areas, with a significant proportion (30.3%) being illiterate, while 60% had education up to higher secondary, and 9.7% were graduates. (Table 1)

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Participants

Parameter	Number of Women (n=175)	Percentage (%)
Age (in years)		
<20	12	6.8
21-25	79	45.2
26-30	44	25.2
31-35	22	12.6
>36	18	10.3
Habitat		
Rural	65	37.2
Urban	110	62.8
Education		
Illiterate	53	30.3
Primary to Higher Secondary	105	60.0

Graduation	17	9.7
Type of Family		
Nuclear Family	105	60.0
Extended Family	70	40.0
Parity		
1	49	28.0
2	87	49.3
>3	39	22.3

In our study, the most common side effect of injectable contraception was irregular bleeding, reported by 60% of participants. Weight gain affected 17.7% of women, followed by headache in 6.8%, and amenorrhea in 5.14%. (Table 2)

Table 2: Side Effects of Injectable Contraception

Parameter	Number of Women (n=175)	Percentage (%)
Side Effects		
Irregular bleeding	105	60.0
Amenorrhea	9	5.14
Weight gain	31	17.7
Headache	12	6.8
Mood changes	4	2.2
No problems	14	8.0

The most common reason for acceptance of injectable contraception was no need for daily administration (49.7%), followed by the ability to breastfeed (28%). Discontinuation was highest after the first injection (54.8%). Key reasons for attrition included side effects (40%) and loss to follow-up (18.3%), with some women discontinuing due to planning pregnancy (17.1%) or finding the repeated doses troublesome (10.3%).

Table 3: Acceptance, Discontinuation, and Attrition

Parameter	Number of Women (n=175)	Percentage (%)
Reasons for Acceptance		
Easy to use	18	10.3
Easy to administer	17	9.7
No need for daily administration	87	49.7
Can breastfeed also	49	28.0
Relieved of monthly bleeding	4	2.3
Discontinuation Rate		
After 1st Injection	96	54.8
After 2nd Injection	41	23.0
After 3rd Injection	19	10.8
After 4th Injection	19	10.8
After 5th Injection	0	0.0
Reasons for Attrition		
Side effects	70	40.0
Lost to follow-up	32	18.3
Planning pregnancy	30	17.1
Missed injection date/changed method	22	12.6
Repeated doses of DMPA are troublesome	18	10.3
Change in mood	3	1.7

Discussion

In our study, the majority of participants accepting injectable contraception were aged 21-25 years, consistent with Singh et al. [9], who also reported peak acceptance in women aged 20-25 years. In contrast, Fonseca et al. [10] found higher acceptance among women aged 26-30 years, reflecting regional differences in reproductive

patterns and contraceptive behaviours. These variations might be attributed to differences in cultural norms, access to family planning services, and healthcare counselling at different stages of reproductive life. Furthermore, we observed that urban residents were more likely to accept injectable contraception, with 62.8% participation, which aligns with Mandloi et al. [11] and Meena et al. [12], who found that urban women were more

inclined toward contraception due to better healthcare access and information availability.

In terms of discontinuation, our study showed that 54.8% of women stopped using the injectable contraceptive after the first injection, with side effects as the main reason. This finding is consistent with Laryea et al. [13] from Ghana, where side effects like irregular bleeding were identified as a significant cause of discontinuation. Similarly, Udealor et al. [14] reported early discontinuation linked to concerns over side effects and challenges such as travel distances to healthcare facilities. In our study, 18.3% of participants were lost to follow-up, a challenge also identified by Kashyap et al. [15], who noted that time constraints and long distances limited women's attendance at family planning clinics.

Educational attainment was another significant factor in contraceptive acceptance. Our study found that 70% of participants had some level of education, supporting findings from Mandloi et al. [11] and Singh et al.⁹, who both concluded that higher education levels are associated with better awareness and acceptance of contraception. Additionally, women from nuclear families in our study exhibited higher acceptance rates, as decision-making tends to be more collaborative within smaller family structures. This observation aligns with findings from Udealor et al. [14], who highlighted the importance of spousal involvement in enhancing contraceptive uptake. Overall, these findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions that address side effects and follow-up challenges, alongside improved counseling efforts to increase the sustained use of injectable contraception.

In our study, irregular bleeding or spotting was the most commonly reported side effect, affecting 60% of participants, followed by weight gain (17.7%), with mood changes being the least frequent. Similarly, Fonseca et al. [10] reported that irregular bleeding was the most prevalent side effect, affecting 63% of participants, underscoring that bleeding irregularities are a significant challenge in maintaining adherence to DMPA use. Laryea et al. [13] also emphasized that irregular bleeding is not only common but may progress to amenorrhea with long-term use. Additionally, Udealor et al. [14] observed that side effects, including bleeding disturbances, contributed to the early discontinuation of contraceptives, highlighting the importance of adequate counseling to manage user expectations. Proper counseling on potential side effects, as recommended by Singh et al. [9] and Mandloi et al. [11], is crucial to mitigate concerns about weight gain, mood changes, and menstrual irregularities. Effective communication about these side effects can enhance adherence by helping

users make informed choices and improving overall satisfaction with DMPA use.

In our study, the primary reason for DMPA acceptance was its convenience, with 49.7% of participants favouring it due to the lack of daily administration. This aligns with findings by Laryea et al. [13] in Ghana, where users preferred injectables due to the ease of administration and longer dosing intervals, minimizing the risk of forgetfulness. Additionally, 9.7% of our participants found the intramuscular injection easy to manage, and lactating women valued that DMPA did not interfere with breastfeeding—a factor also emphasized by Udealor et al. [14], who reported that breastfeeding mothers are more inclined to adopt contraceptives that do not affect milk production. The practical advantages of DMPA resonate with Mandloi et al. [11], who highlighted that user-friendly contraceptive methods tend to have higher acceptance rates, especially when access to healthcare services is limited. However, while the initial acceptance is high, sustained usage requires overcoming common barriers, including user education and support.

Despite its advantages, side effects emerged as the most common reason for attrition in our study, accounting for 40% of dropouts. This is consistent with Fonseca et al. [10], who found that irregular bleeding and weight gain were major factors for discontinuation. In our study, the highest discontinuation rate occurred after the first injection (54.8%), a pattern echoed by Fonseca et al. [10], where most users dropped out after the initial or second dose. Laryea et al. [13] similarly identified that early dropout often occurs when side effects are not adequately addressed, with factors such as irregular bleeding contributing to dissatisfaction. Furthermore, 18.2% of participants in our study were lost to follow-up, which aligns with findings from Kashyap et al. [15], where time constraints and travel distance impeded consistent clinic attendance. Udealor et al. [14] also noted that remote living conditions and limited healthcare access are significant contributors to non-adherence. The sociocultural context plays a crucial role, as women from rural areas or with limited healthcare access face additional challenges in maintaining regular contraceptive use. Mood changes, although the least common reason for discontinuation (1.7%), still indicate the need for comprehensive counselling, as suggested by Singh et al. [9], to ensure users are fully informed about potential side effects, fostering better adherence and satisfaction.

Our study has several limitations that may influence the generalizability of the findings. First, the relatively small sample size and focus on participants from a single tertiary care center may not capture the broader contraceptive behaviours

and challenges faced by women in different regions. Additionally, the study relied on self-reported data, which may introduce recall bias or underreporting of certain side effects and reasons for discontinuation. Follow-up attrition also posed a challenge, as some participants were lost to follow-up, limiting our ability to assess long-term adherence and outcomes. Furthermore, the influence of sociocultural factors and healthcare accessibility could not be fully explored due to the lack of detailed qualitative data.

Conclusion

Injectable contraception is a safe, convenient, and effective long-term contraceptive option that becomes more acceptable when accompanied by quality counselling and consistent follow-up care. Proper management of side effects and timely follow-ups can significantly reduce discontinuation rates. However, despite its benefits, it remains less popular than female sterilization, underscoring the need for increased awareness and education about its advantages. Injectable contraceptives are particularly suitable for lactating women, as they provide effective birth spacing without impacting the quality or quantity of breast milk. With free availability through government programs, efforts should be intensified to promote its use, ensuring that a broader population benefits from its contraceptive and health-related advantages.

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